

Title: **A standard protocol for describing the evaluation of ecological models**

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Abstract

Numerical models of ecological systems are increasingly used by scientists to address complex environmental questions. One challenge for scientists, managers, and stakeholders is to appraise the performance of these models to answer specific questions of scientific or societal relevance, that is to perform, communicate or access transparent evaluations of ecological models. While there have been substantial developments to support standardised descriptions of ecological models, less has been done to standardise and to report model evaluation practices. We present here a general protocol designed to guide the reporting of model evaluation. The protocol is organised in three major parts: the *objective(s)* of the modelling application, the ecological *patterns* of relevance and the *evaluation* methodology proper, and is termed the OPE (objectives, patterns, evaluation) protocol. We present the 25 questions of the OPE protocol which address the many aspects of the evaluation process and then apply them to six case studies based on a diversity of ecological models. In addition to standardising and increasing the transparency of the model evaluation process, we find that going through the OPE protocol helps modellers to think more deeply about the evaluation of their models. From this last point, we suggest that it would be highly beneficial for modellers to consider the OPE early in the modelling process, in addition to using it as a reporting tool and as a reviewing tool.

Keywords

Standardisation, best practice, ecological patterns, skill assessment, transparency.

1. Introduction

Scientists, managers, and stakeholders increasingly rely on numerical models of ecological systems. One challenge is to appraise the efficiency of these models to tackle complex environmental questions. Providing clear evaluations of model performance is one way to address this challenge. Models are constructed, analysed and used by different actors, from scientists to policymakers, and these actors have different understandings and expectations from models. Assessing how good a model is at addressing specific problems is difficult when ecological modellers use a variety of model types, have different modelling cultures and practices, and use different vocabularies. This can hinder communication, transparency, reproducibility, and the general development of good practices within the modelling community. It is therefore essential to provide tools to support a common understanding of what can be expected from a model and how a model is to be validated (Cartwright et al. 2016; Eker et al. 2018).

Transparency and reproducibility are at the core of the scientific method. However, the complexity of the tools used to observe and model ecological systems challenges reproducibility and transparency (Powers and Hampton 2019). The ongoing so-called reproducibility or replicability crisis reflects this difficulty, although the crisis has primarily been identified in the fields of psychology (Pashler and Wagenmakers 2012), clinical studies (Begley and Ioannidis John 2015) and economics (Camerer et al. 2016). It is much less discussed in ecological research (but see Ives 2018; Nichols et al. 2019, 2021). It may not be possible to strictly replicate ecological observations, but transparency in workflow and data analyses can facilitate reproducibility. It is nevertheless possible to reproduce ecological model simulations, given that the relevant information is provided for that purpose. In addition to replicating a model and the associated simulations, it is equally important to be able to understand, assess and replicate how model performance was evaluated. This step is critical, given that almost every new method published are claimed to outperform existing ones, but are seldom re-evaluated (Boulesteix et al. 2020). Providing relevant and comprehensive information is a first step towards replicability, which needs to be complemented by appropriate communication and quality standards. How is the information communicated? Is it accessible? Is it unambiguous? Is it sufficient? A standardised protocol for reporting model evaluation procedures would address these questions and contribute to increased transparency and reproducibility of ecological models.

There have been considerable collective efforts in recent decades to develop standardized modelling practices, from model building to evaluation of model performances. A major advancement has been the development of standardised protocols such as the ODD (Overview, Design concepts, and Details, Grimm *et al.* 2006). The ODD protocol was originally developed to respond to the lack of a standard protocol for describing individual based models (IBMs). The protocol was reviewed and updated twice since its original publication (Grimm *et al.* 2010, 2020) and it is now commonly used by ecological modellers, beyond the original IBM community, to describe their models in reports and publications. The ODD protocol has been inspirational to groups of modellers with diverse focus, such as on model optimisation (ODDO, Mahévas 2019), data-mapping (ODD+2D, Laatabi *et al.* 2018), and inclusion of human decisions (ODD+D, Müller *et al.* 2013). In each case these groups have borrowed from the original ODD protocol idea and extended it for their specific purpose, thereby contributing to the harmonisation and communication of modelling practices.

An important step in the development and application of ecological models is the evaluation phase. There exists a large body of literature on how to perform model evaluation for various classes of models (e.g. Stow *et al.* 2009; Allen and Somerfield 2009; Bennett *et al.* 2013; Conn *et al.* 2018; Hipsey *et al.* 2020), but much less work has been done to standardise the reporting of model evaluations. The TRACE (TRANSPARENT and Comprehensive Ecological modelling) documentation (Grimm *et al.* 2014) is a notable exception which provides a framework for documenting the modelling process, including several aspects of model evaluation. Standardised protocols for reporting model evaluation can constitute useful tools for modellers and end-users to easily understand and compare evaluation procedures and appreciate the performance of models in relation to specific objectives. Making such tools available is therefore anticipated to benefit the scientific community and model end-users.

The issue of model validation and evaluation in environmental science has been the subject of extensive research and debate. Oreskes (1998) argued that quantitative models cannot be validated but only evaluated. In Oreskes' view, evaluation is described as “an assessment in which both positive and negative results are possible, and where the grounds on which a model is declared good enough are clearly articulated”. This assessment implies an examination of model outputs against pre-specified performance criteria. In the literature, the term *model validation* has remained pervasive (Eker *et al.* 2019) although often overlapping with the concept of evaluation as originally presented by Oreskes. In their 10-step procedure for developing and evaluating environmental models, Jakeman *et al.* (2006) introduced a stepwise

approach in which every stage is open to critical review and revision, in consort with end-users. The evaluation step is left to the end and is concerned with the model being *fit for purpose*, although the criteria for achieving this goal are not fully developed. More recently, Parker (2020) explores the meaning of a model being *adequate for purpose* for different classes of models, whether pedagogical, explanatory or predictive. In the works of Jakeman and Parker, model evaluation is primarily achieved by measuring the performance of a model against pre-specified objectives, thereby following the original argument of Oreskes. This excludes the idea of a *general validity* of a model and favours the principle of an evaluation of a model for a specific objective (or a set of objectives). This mirrors George Box's notorious statement that "*all models are wrong; the practical question is how wrong do they have to be to not be useful*" (Box and Draper 1987), where *useful* implies use and therefore purpose. This also is in line with Augusiak's review of the literature on model evaluation and validation which concludes that despite little agreement on terms and underlying notions in the literature, it has repeatedly been pointed out that the evaluation of a model should depend on its *purpose* (Augusiak et al. 2014).

Evaluating that an ecological model is fit for purpose implies that the same model can (and should) be evaluated each time it is used for a new purpose. This is a rather trivial implication of the *fit for purpose* evaluation, however examples of re-evaluation of the performance of complex ecological models are scarce. Complex ecological models require extensive development efforts, and these materialise in the first publication of the model, together with a global evaluation (or validation) of the model (see e.g., Radach and Moll 2006; Link et al. 2010; Travers-Trolet et al. 2014; Pedersen et al. 2021). A fit-for-purpose approach would require that this first model evaluation be revised and reported for each new application of the model. One challenge in doing so is that the task of reporting model evaluation, which is already substantial when the model is first published, may seem daunting if it is to be repeated for every new model application. This can possibly be eased by reporting primarily on aspects of the model evaluation that are specific to each new application. An additional help can be provided by following a template in which a set of questions can guide the modeller through the reporting process.

By taking inspiration from the success and utility of the ODD protocol and the following extensions, we here present a complementary protocol for the reporting of ecological model evaluation procedures: the OPE (Objectives, Patterns, Evaluation) protocol. We discuss the rationale for the different elements of this protocol and provide a list of questions that can guide

modellers to report in OPE format. We summarise the protocol (Table 1) and provide an easy-to-use Word template to support documenting model evaluations. (Supplementary material S1). Finally, we test the protocol on six case studies taken from a collection of marine ecosystem models with which the authors are familiar. These case studies are presented in detail in the supplementary material (S2). These modelling applications pre-existed the OPE protocol. The OPE has therefore not been used to guide the model evaluations presented here, but only to report how these evaluations were performed.

2. Elements of the OPE protocol

The elements of the OPE protocol are divided in three sections: Objectives, Patterns and Evaluation. Each section is then divided in subsections which contain one to six questions.

2.1. Objectives

2.1.1. Context and motivations

We recognize that many environmental models are not developed with the sole purpose of answering a single, well circumscribed question. Rather, models take time to develop and are gradually applied to a range of questions. Models of natural systems are inevitably embedded with multiple sources of uncertainty, and modellers make decisions during model construction (e.g., on which processes to include or simplify) which will affect the final outcome (Babel *et al.* 2019). There is a risk that assumptions which are reasonable for one particular model application are inadequate for another (Parker 2020; Saltelli *et al.* 2020). It is therefore essential that model suitability and performance are assessed and described for each application, and a crucial first step is describing the purpose of the specific application. In other words, to evaluate that a model is fit for purpose one must first specify the purpose. In this contribution, we refer to *model* as the generic description of the modelling tool (e.g. Ecopath, Atlantis, NorCPM1)(e.g. Ecopath with Ecosim, Polovina 1984; Christensen and Walters 2004), we use the terms *goal*, *purpose* and *objective* in an interchangeable manner to express the motivation driving the study and we refer to a model *application* when the model is applied towards a pre-defined objective or set of objectives. Central in the OPE framework is our conception that it is sensible to evaluate the same model against different patterns or data when applied for different purposes. Describing the main objectives of the study and how modelling will contribute to reach these objectives is perhaps the most important step in evaluating model performance and suitability, and it should be a key reference point throughout the evaluation process. Without a clear

understanding of the purpose, it becomes difficult to communicate credibility and generate trust in the modelling work. Furthermore, it may be sensible to evaluate the same model against very different patterns or data when applied for different purposes. Defining the aims and objectives of the model application early in the research process can save time, for instance with the realisation that objectives may depend on key processes for which the model of choice lacks functionality.

The aims and objectives of a model application should be stated in simple, clear language. We suggest using active sentences (e.g., construct, produce, test, document) and avoid vague wordings (e.g. explore, study, investigate). Beware that ambiguity in the description of the purpose of a model often leads to multiple (subjective) interpretations of whether an outcome was successful or not (Parker 2020). This hinders a reliable evaluation process. The following questions guide the reporting of objectives:

1. What are the objectives of the model application?
2. Why is the model suitable to address the objectives?
3. What would count as successful in achieving these objectives?

2.1.2. Specific model setup

Optimally, the ecological model has already been fully described following a standardized protocol such as the ODD. It is possible that the original description is adequate for a new application of the model, but specific applications may also require adjustments of the model structure, parameters, or assumptions. Assumptions are particularly important to report when the model is used to perform predictions at other points in time and space (Wenger and Olden 2012; Yates et al. 2018). This is the case when the objective of the model is to produce forecasts or to predict ecosystem properties in one region based on a model developed in another. It is wise to explicitly state what lies behind the often-implicit assumption of *ceteris paribus* (everything else being equal). For example, are trophic interactions assumed to follow the same rules in different regions? Are spatial distributions or environmental conditions assumed to be unchanged in the future? When models are used for conditional forecasting, one should also report assumptions about expected changes that can affect the system studied. For example, how are possible future changes in water temperature, fishing effort, accidental oil spill or increase in noise due to shipping represented in the model? A model can be revised to better reproduce the ecological components or processes that are relevant to a new application. It is also possible that revised estimates of input parameters or new data on the forcing conditions

of the model become available. All these updates should be reported in this section which describes any changes or additions which have been made since the original model description.

4. Are there any deviations from the original model description?
 - a. In the model assumptions,
 - b. in the model structure (e.g. addition of submodels, variables, components, modifications of spatial or temporal scales),
 - c. in the model details (e.g. changes in parameter values, functional relationships),
 - d. in the model forcing (e.g. initial conditions, boundary conditions, forcing time series and maps).

2.2. Patterns

2.2.1. Selected patterns

A *pattern* may be defined as a characteristic and clearly identifiable structure in nature, or in data extracted from nature (e.g., population cycles, animal space use, species diversity etc.), that can be attributed to a generative process (Levin 1992; Grimm et al. 1996). Thus defined, a pattern is key to ecological understanding and prediction. Ecological patterns emerge from multiple ecological processes, which operate at multiple spatial and temporal scales and levels of organization (individual, population, community, and ecosystem). Understanding the causal mechanisms responsible for pattern formation is a primary goal of ecology (Levin 1992).

Modelling complex adaptive systems (see Levin 1992), such as marine ecosystems, is challenging, but pattern-oriented modelling (POM) may facilitate the task (Grimm et al. 1996, 2005; Grimm and Railsback 2012). POM “starts with identifying a set of patterns observed at multiple scales and levels that characterize a system with respect to the particular problem being modelled” (Grimm and Railsback 2012). In other words, the selection of patterns to be used in model evaluation, depends on the objective or hypothesis of the study.

Relevant ecological patterns may be related to numbers, biomass, production, or consumption of relevant ecological entities, to dynamic behaviour at equilibrium, or to character of state transitions in perturbation studies or in systems undergoing change (e.g. Beisner et al. 2003). Other examples are spatial patterns such as spatial synchrony or traveling waves (e.g. Sherratt and Smith 2008). More complex emerging patterns (e.g., spatial structure described by a variogram, degree of spatial overlap between species) may also be candidate targets for model evaluation. The selection of specific patterns is motivated by the objectives of the modelling

application and is generally driven by the hypotheses that can explain the emergence of these patterns. It is therefore critical to report on the selection of patterns and on the justification for this selection.

5. Which ecological patterns are used for the model evaluation?
 - a. temporal patterns such as cycles, regime shift or trends, measures of temporal variability, and autocorrelation.
 - b. spatial patterns such as spatial synchrony, traveling waves, patchiness and autocorrelation.
 - c. structural and functional patterns, such as taxonomic diversity, biomass ratios, integrated production, diet fractions, and trait distributions.
6. Why are these patterns important/essential to address the objectives?

In the following part of the OPE one must describe the data used for evaluation purposes, which can include both data from the model output and data which are independent of the model. Information on data used for model building should be provided in the model description (typically, an ODD protocol) and data used for optimization should be reported in the optimization description (e.g. in an ODDO protocol, Mahévas 2019).

2.2.2. Independent data

Independent data – that is data that exists independently of the model being built – are often derived from field observations, and procedures for collecting and processing these observations should briefly be summarized in this part of the OPE. Relevant information includes i) whether the data originate from a dedicated field survey, an open database, or another model, ii) the spatial/ temporal/ taxonomic/ etc. extent and resolution of the data, iii) data representativeness, and iv) accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty. Data representativeness is the degree to which data can be used to represent the ecological patterns that are relevant for the objective of the study. For example, daily, weekly or monthly time-series will have different representativeness if the ecological pattern of interest is phenology. Similarly, the representativeness of data collected at a single sampling station is also expected to vary with the spatial scale of the ecological question of concern, being more representative for small scale modelling studies centred around the sampling station than for larger scale investigations. Deriving ecological patterns (section 2.2.1) from observations can involve extensive data processing, and this should be reported here. When the same type of data can be used for model optimisation and evaluation (as in cross validation) this should be reported in

this section. In some cases, although the data is collected independently of the model being built, the model and data may not be completely independent from each other (for example, knowledge from historical data used to build the model, or input data in an Ecopath model is also expressed as an output of the model) and this should be reported. The following questions guide the collection of information about the independent data used to evaluate the model, given selected pattern(s).

7. Where do the independent data originate from?

Field survey, open database, another model, ...

8. What are the extent and resolution of the independent data?

Spatially, temporally, taxonomically, ...

9. How representative are the independent data of the ecological process?

10. Are there estimates of independent data accuracy, precision, bias or uncertainty?

11. How are the independent data processed to represent the selected patterns and are assumptions made to derive these patterns from the data?

2.2.3. Model outputs

Often, only parts of the model outputs are used in a specific application and the aim of this section is to describe which outputs have been used and evaluated. In some cases, the data may be post-processed (e.g. aggregation of results by guild, geographical region or integration in time). The purpose of post-processing can be to generate indicators of the relevant patterns (ex. species spatial distribution, biomass ratios, index of seasonality, see section 2.2.1) or to generate model outputs that are comparable with independent data (section 2.2.2). The post processing step can require new assumptions (e.g., assume that conversion rates such as C:Chla are constant in time/space/taxa). The aim of this section is to describe the selection of model outputs, the post-processing operations, and to report on quality, quantity, representativeness, uncertainties, or potential bias in the model outputs.

12. Which model outputs are used for the evaluation?

13. Have the outputs been post-processed, and how?

14. Are there estimates of model outputs accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?

15. Are additional assumptions made when deriving patterns from model outputs?

2.3. Evaluation

2.3.1. Evaluation methodology

We refer here to the evaluation method applied in the context of a specific application of a model to address stated objectives (section 2.1.1). Model verification (*sensu* Grabner 2018) - the act of testing whether the model does what it is supposed to do, i.e., that it is technically functional - should precede any application of the model and is not considered here. A first model evaluation step is often to conduct *sanity checks*. These are rapid explorations of the model outputs which ensure that, even though the model is technically functional, it is not behaving poorly. Sanity checks are often non-quantitative and based on domain knowledge rather than on quantitative comparisons of observations vs. model outputs. Though these are not often reported in model evaluation procedures, they inform about key conditions that the model must satisfy to be considered useful. Examples of sanity checks can include an inspection that population sizes or biomasses are within plausible ranges, that seasonal patterns are plausible or that emerging spatial patterns are visually credible. These can be done via Fermi estimations, often referred to as ‘back of the envelope’ calculations of plausible ranges.

16. Are sanity checks conducted? If so, what is the method used?

- a. Which data and patterns are used for this?
- b. Does this apply to patterns that are not otherwise evaluated for this model application?

The core of the evaluation process is the comparison of patterns emerging from model outputs against those obtained from independent observations. This first raises the issue of the comparability between independent observations and model outputs, i.e., whether model outputs and independent data are directly comparable and whether modelled patterns are directly comparable to observed patterns. For example, are modelled biomass integrated over a large continuous geographical domain comparable with biomass field observations from a limited number of sampling sites? The second issue is the methodology used to compare ecological patterns derived from observations to those derived from the model. There can be many methodological approaches, ranging from qualitative visual comparisons to fully quantitative estimates of the model performance at reproducing observed patterns (Allen and Somerfield 2009; Bennett *et al.* 2013). The latter can include univariate or multivariate approaches, and can be based on error-based measures, information theory measures,

parametric tests, non-parametric tests, distance-based measures or combined measures (Hora and Campos 2015). This stage of the evaluation is sometimes referred to as *skill assessment*.

The choice of methods and metrics used in model skills evaluation will depend on the relevant patterns. For example, when dealing with cycles, the degree of congruence between modelled and observed cycles amplitude and frequency should be reported. When modelling state transitions, agreement in the rate of change of a trend should be reported. With ecosystem models addressing ecological stability or temporal variability, the stability measure should be reported at multiple levels of organisation (e.g., species, functional group, community etc). The quantitative criteria to evaluate the match between observed and simulated patterns must be reported. For example, if the mean of the simulations is within a certain range (e.g. 1 standard deviation) of the observed pattern, the model satisfactorily addresses the pattern (e.g. Kramer-Schadt et al. 2007). Each methodology usually comes with associated assumptions that need fulfilling for the method to be valid, and these should also be reported here.

The core issue at the end of the evaluation process is whether or not the model outputs can be considered satisfying for the purpose of answering the modelling objective, i.e., that the grounds on which a model is declared good enough are clearly articulated (Oreskes 1998).

17. What is the methodology used to compare ecological patterns derived from independent data with patterns derived from the model?
 - a. What is the rationale for choosing this method?
 - b. How are observational and/or model output uncertainties handled?
 - c. Does the methodology rely on specific assumptions?
18. Is there a threshold level (in the match between observed and modelled patterns) that can separate acceptable from unacceptable models?
19. How comparable are the patterns derived from the model and those derived from the independent data?

By answering the above questions, researchers should also discuss if there are patterns that cannot be well evaluated with the chosen method.

2.3.2. Sensitivities

We distinguish between two types of sensitivities to be reported. First, *model sensitivity* which is the result of a sensitivity analysis (SA), usually performed on model structure and parameters.

Second, *evaluation method sensitivity*, which refers to the sensitivity of the model evaluation to the choice of evaluation methodology and available observational data.

Sensitivity analysis (SA) scrutinizes how variations in model inputs influence variations in model outputs, a fundamental step in model evaluation and corroboration (EPA 2009). A diverse array of SA approaches has been developed to help cope with the various needs dictated by differing model assumptions, computational complexity and availability of relevant information (Saltelli et al. 2004; EPA 2009). Reviews and guidelines for best SA practice in the context of ecological and environmental modelling are an important aid to SA planning, implementation, and reporting (Saltelli et al. 2004, 2021; EPA 2009; Pianosi et al. 2016).

Attributes of SA methods worth considering in reporting include: independence of model linearity and additivity assumptions, ability to address interaction effects among input factors, capacity to handle differences in scale and shape of input probability distribution functions, ability to deal with differences in input spatial and temporal dimensions, and capacity to evaluate the effect of an input while all other inputs are allowed to vary as well (Frey 2002; Saltelli et al. 2004).

In this section, one should consider the sensitivity of the model outputs that are relevant to the objective of the study i.e., the modelled *patterns* (section 2.2.3). Priority should be given to reporting sensitivity analyses that were conducted specifically for the model application. Sensitivity analyses performed in earlier stages of model development can be reported if also relevant for the objective(s) of the study.

20. Has a model sensitivity analysis been performed? How?

- a. on the model structure?
- b. on the model parametrization?
- c. on other aspects of the model?

21. Which elements are the modelled patterns most sensitive to?

- a. input parameters
- b. priors and assumptions
- c. structural elements

22. How sensitive are the modelled patterns to the choice of initial conditions, boundary conditions, spatial and temporal resolution?

While there is no perfect model to address a specific ecological question, there is no perfect method either to evaluate the performance of a model (Makridakis et al. 2020). Typically, the choice of the sensitivity analyses depends on the availability of observational data with which the model can be compared, on the computational requirements to perform certain types of model evaluation, and on the availability of evaluation methodologies to the modellers. This section reports on the rationale and criteria for choosing a particular approach to evaluate the model performance, stressing when the choices are dictated by the objectives of the study as opposed to computational constraints, lack of relevant information or other considerations. For example, run times for complex simulation models impose restrictions on the parameter space, thus limiting the scope for global SA and simultaneous exploration of known sources of uncertainty, two desirable features of SA in relation to the objectives of the study. This section also reports on how sensitive the evaluation method is to the data used for evaluation (section 2.4). Could the model evaluation give significantly different results if other/new/more precise data were used? In summary, this section highlights the relevant attributes of the model evaluation, caveats, and possible limitations, clarifying the implications of the model evaluation in relation to the objectives.

23. How sensitive is the model evaluation to availability and uncertainty of the independent data?
24. How much is the model evaluation constrained by computational or theoretical limits?
25. How does the perceived performance of the model depend on the chosen evaluation methodology?

3. OPE template

As a practical tool, we provide in Table 1 a summary of the OPE protocol which highlight the main sections of the protocol, the 25 questions as well as guidelines on how to answer them. We also provide in supplementary material (S1), a Word template that can be used to directly input information relevant to a modelling study.

Table 1. The 25 questions of the OPE protocol, grouped into three headings: Objectives, Patterns and Evaluation. A brief comment accompanies each question to guide the reporting. A template form is provided in appendix S1, in which reporting can be directly entered.

	#	Question	Comments
OBJECTIVES CONTEXT AND MOTIVATIONS	1	What are the objectives of the model application?	<i>Describe here the motivation and context for using the model. What is the purpose of the study? Do not describe the model, or its general objectives but focus on study-specific objectives. Use active sentences (e.g., produce, test, quantify, reconstruct dynamics) and avoid vague wordings (e.g. explore, study, investigate, understand).</i>
	2	Why is the model suitable to address the objectives?	<i>Provide the main rationale for why this specific model approach is suited to address the objective(s) raised in question 1. For example, is the model representing a process that is central to addressing the objectives?</i>
	3	What would count as successful in achieving these objectives?	<i>Explain here which criteria are used to determine if the model can address the objective or not. For example, if the objective of the model is to quantify a variable/process, is success defined based on the uncertainty around these estimated quantities?</i>
SPECIFIC MODEL SETUP	4	Are there any deviations from the original model description? a. In the model assumptions? b. In the model structure – submodels, variables, components, scales? c. In the model details – parameter values, functional relationships	<i>If this is the first time the model is presented, a full ODD description should be provided (Grimm et al., 2006, 2010, 2020). If the model has already been presented elsewhere, only deviations from the original description should be provided here. Models are often adjusted to address a specific ecological question/objective. It is these adjustments that should be reported here.</i>

#	Question	Comments
d.	In the model forcing – initial conditions, boundary conditions, observation forcing, maps?	
5	Which ecological patterns are used for the model evaluation?	<p><i>The term "ecological pattern" refers to Pattern Oriented Modelling (POM, Grimm et al., 1996, 2005; Grimm and Railsback, 2012). Relevant ecological patterns can be observed at various scales and characterize the ecological system with respect to the particular problem being modelled. The patterns listed in a, b, and c are by no mean required or exhaustive, but are provided as examples of possibly relevant patterns.</i></p>
	a. Temporal patterns – cycles, shifts, trends, variability, autocorrelation	
	b. Spatial patterns – synchrony, travelling waves, patchiness, autocorrelation	
c.	Structural, functional patterns – diversity, biomass ratio, integrated production, diet, traits	
6	Why are these patterns important/essential to address the objectives?	<p><i>Explain here how the selection of ecological patterns is justified in relation to the objectives of the modelling application. Are there hypotheses that can explain the emergence of these patterns? Do not discuss how these patterns can be derived from observations or model outputs, this is addressed in questions 11-15.</i></p>
7	Where do the independent data originate from?	<p><i>Independent data refers to data that exists independently from the current model being developed. These can be observational data or outputs from other models. Do not discuss outputs from the modelling study, these are addressed in questions 12-15.</i></p>
8	What are the extent and resolution of the independent data?	<p><i>Report here the spatial, temporal, taxonomic extent and resolution of the independent data identified in question 7. For example, if a data series is presented, what are the starting and ending time and the time-frequency of data acquisition; if</i></p>

#	Question	Comments
		<i>biodiversity data is provided, what is the taxonomic resolution and the method used to determine taxonomic units.</i>
9	How representative are the independent data of the ecological processes?	<i>This is a follow-up from question 8 to link data with key processes and patterns. For example, if a central process in the study is interannual variations in population numbers, and observational data of population numbers are available: do these data appropriately represent the annual abundance, or do they represent a snapshot in time or space? Do not report on uncertainty estimates here, this is addressed in question 10.</i>
10	Are there estimates of independent data accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?	<i>Uncertainty estimates for the independent data should be reported here (uncertainty estimates for the model outputs are reported in question 14).</i>
11	How are the independent data processed to represent the selected pattern and are assumptions made to derive these patterns from the data?	<i>Independent data – whether observational or modelled – may provide a representation of the patterns of interest (question 5) only after further processing. For example, survey data may be spatially interpolated to derive spatial distribution patterns. Another example: biomasses from several taxonomic units may be grouped to derive patterns of interannual changes in biomass for particular functional groups. Report these post-processing steps here.</i>
MODEL OUTPUTS	12 Which model outputs are used for the evaluation?	<i>This is a list of model outputs that have been selected based on the modelling objectives and related ecological patterns. The full set of raw outputs, which is often large, unprocessed, and not</i>

#	Question	Comments
		<p><i>targeted towards the specific objectives of the modelling study, should not be reported here.</i></p>
	<p>13 Have the outputs been post-processed, and how?</p>	<p><i>As for independent data, model outputs may provide a representation of the patterns of interest only after further processing (see question 11). Report here the post-processing steps that are used to go from raw model outputs to ecologically relevant patterns.</i></p>
	<p>14 Are there estimates of model output accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?</p>	<p><i>Uncertainty estimates for the model outputs should be reported here. Focus should be on model outputs that are used for the model evaluation.</i></p>
	<p>15 Are additional assumptions made when deriving patterns from model outputs?</p>	<p><i>Report here when some assumptions may be required to derive outputs at the appropriate scale or in the appropriate units. For example a dry:wet weight ratio may be assumed across species/seasons/areas to derive weight wet estimates (the relevant pattern) from dry weight (the model output).</i></p>
<p>EVALUATION EVALUATION METHODOLOGY</p>	<p>16 Are sanity checks conducted? If so, what is the method used?</p> <p>a. Which data and patterns are used for this?</p> <p>b. Does this apply to patterns that are not otherwise evaluated for this model application?</p>	<p><i>Sanity checks are informal steps that are taken throughout model development to ensure that the model is not behaving badly. They inform on key conditions that the model must satisfy to be considered useful. For example, checking that a population neither becomes extinct nor grows to unrealistic size.</i></p>

#	Question	Comments	
17	What is the methodology used to compare ecological patterns derived from independent data with patterns from the model?	<i>This section describes how model outputs are evaluated against independent data. This is sometimes referred to as model "skill assessment". This section should describe the methodology used as well as the rationale for the choice of methods, i.e. how the methods relates to data, model outputs, objectives of the study, and relevant ecological patterns.</i>	
a.	What is the rationale for choosing this method?		
b.	How are observational and/or model output uncertainties handled?		
c.	Does the methodology rely on specific assumptions?		
18	Is there a threshold level (match between observed and modelled patterns) that can separate acceptable from unacceptable models?	<i>When are the model outputs reliable enough to be used to answer the main question of the study? Answering this question is critical to evaluate when the model can address the main objective of the study. One should not discuss here the conclusions of the study, but only the skill level required to consider the model useful.</i>	
19	How comparable are the patterns derived from the model and those derived from the independent data?	<i>This section describes the result of the model skill assessment, plus any other qualitative features (patterns) that can be compared between model outputs and independent data.</i>	
SENSITIVITIES	20	Has a model sensitivity analysis been performed, and how?	<i>This section describes the approach used to conduct model sensitivity analyses (SA), in a broad sense, from individual parameter SA to global SA. Various aspect of the methods used for SA can be reported here, including sensitivity to parameters, model structure, boundary/initial conditions, simulation design, and so on (see e.g. Pianosi et al. 2016).</i>
	a.	on the model structure?	
	b.	on the model parametrization?	

#	Question	Comments
21	Which elements are the modelled patterns most sensitive to? a. input parameters b. priors and assumptions c. structural elements	<i>If applicable, report here the results of the SA on parameters, model structure and assumptions.</i>
22	How sensitive are the modelled patterns to the choice of initial conditions, boundary conditions, spatial and temporal resolution?	<i>If applicable, report here the results of the SA on the choice of initial conditions, spin-up time, boundary conditions, spatial and temporal resolution.</i>
23	How sensitive is the model evaluation to the independent data availability and uncertainty?	<i>Could the model evaluation give significantly different results if other, new, or more precise data were used than those described in question 7?</i>
24	How much is the model evaluation constrained by computational or theoretical limits?	<i>Models that are structurally simple and computationally fast can generally be explored through in-depth SA. It is more demanding to run appropriate SA on models that are structurally complex or that use substantial CPU resources to run. For some models, complexity & run time make SA non-achievable in practice. These issues should be reported here.</i>
25	How does the perceived performance of the model depend on the chosen evaluation methodology?	<i>Could the model evaluation give significantly different results if another evaluation approach had been used (other than reported in question 17)?</i>

4. Applications

We provide in the supplementary material (S2) examples of applications of the OPE protocol in the context of six modelling applications:

1. an Individual Based Model (IBM) used to quantify uncertainties in the estimates of mean biomass of the copepod *Calanus finmarchicus* as a function of sampling design,
2. a statistical food-web model used to quantify the association between capelin (*Mallotus villosus*) and its main two prey (krill and *Calanus* species),
3. simulations from the Non-Deterministic Network Dynamics (NDND) model to assess the persistence of trophic controls in the Barents Sea,
4. an Ecopath model to estimate trophic positions for ecological groups in the Barents Sea,
5. the Nordic and Barents Seas Atlantis Model (NoBa) simulations to assess cumulative impact of fisheries and climate in the Norwegian and Barents Seas, and
6. the reconstructions and predictions of selected physical and biogeochemical properties using the NorCPM1 model in the Barents Sea

These case studies cover a range of modelling practices, modelling tools and study objectives. Knowledge about context within which a model is developed and of the history of the model development is essential to understand the evaluation approach. We realise that the OPE case studies presented in this manuscript can be difficult to read without prior knowledge of each model context and history. In stand-alone modelling studies, model descriptions would normally be provided in full, but this is not the case here. To correct for this, we included introductory paragraphs that describe the models that were used in each case study and provide a brief history of the models, i.e. where they originate from and how they evolved to finally be used in the current case studies.

5. Discussion

The OPE protocol as we present it here is complementing other reporting protocols, in particular the ODD protocol and the extensions (e.g. ODDO, ODD+D), by focusing on the model evaluation. We argue that such a protocol can significantly contribute to improving model evaluation and can in general increase transparency and reproducibility of published models.

Model evaluation is essential and should accompany all model studies. We have therefore developed the OPE protocol for model evaluation, which is generic enough to apply to a wide range of ecological modelling studies, from coupled physical-chemical-biological systems (NORWECOM.E2E, NorCPM1, Atlantis), to simpler models focussed on food-webs interactions (NDND, Ecopath, Gompertz). In our experience, most modellers consider their model as somewhat special (i.e., not like other models) and therefore assume that it would be difficult to evaluate models using a standardised protocol like the OPE. Indeed, we found that it was often work-demanding for modellers to answer the 25 questions of the OPE protocol. Through the six case studies, we identified several challenges in documenting the OPE. Documenting model evaluation is not a standard step in most modelling studies. Lack of experience and training in doing so made it a time-consuming and demanding task that required several iterations, and substantial amount of thinking and discussion. At times, the OPE exercise was perceived as too time-consuming, little rewarding in the short term and easy to postpone. It was often difficult to find the balance between providing informative answers and remaining concise. In several cases, it was not always obvious what was the right amount of contextual information required to inform readers about the model. When sensitivity analysis had been performed in earlier studies, it could be unclear how much this should be reported. At first sight, some questions appeared unclear or redundant, though these issues were usually resolved after some iterations. Some questions were also of little relevance for some of the model applications explored here. Nevertheless, it was possible to successfully apply the OPE protocol to each specific case study, despite the diverse collection of model types. We therefore anticipate that the protocol will be applicable to many ecological modelling studies.

The protocol can be used from the start of a modelling study, to guide model evaluation throughout the study. Though the primary motivation for this protocol was to construct a tool to help modellers reporting how they evaluated their models given specific objectives, we found that answering the protocol questions for the individual case studies led to additional discussions and reflexions on model evaluation. In some instances, it was identified that additional evaluation steps could be taken or that some steps in the evaluation process could have been better specified. In the case of the Gompertz case study, documenting the OPE revealed that posterior predictive checks could have been considered to improve the evaluation. In the NDND case study, it was only after the OPE was documented that the issue of determining a threshold between acceptable and unacceptable models became clear. In the NoBa case study, it became apparent that many aspects of model evaluation for a complex end-

to-end model like Atlantis, were still under-developed, and that the OPE could guide future work towards improved model evaluation methodology. In all case studies the OPE helped to clarify existing evaluation procedures and identify possible improvements. Had the OPE been available at the start of these studies, the model evaluation would likely have been conducted more thoroughly. This highlights the potential utility of the OPE to stimulate higher standard of model evaluation, in addition to its original goal of merely reporting how evaluation was conducted.

It is important to note that the OPE protocol goes far beyond model skill assessment. Assessing the prediction skill of ecological models has been the focus of recent literature (see e.g. Stow *et al.*, 2009, Olsen *et al.*, 2016 or Steenbeck *et al.*, 2021 and references therein). Skill assessment is an integral part of model evaluation and is clearly identified in the first part of the *Evaluation* section of the OPE protocol (questions 17-19). The OPE protocol expands beyond skill assessment by addressing issues related to objective, patterns, data and sensitivity analyses and puts balanced focus on these different elements.

Documenting model evaluation is not yet standard practice. The 25 questions outlined in the OPE protocol are a guide to present an extensive – but not exhaustive – description of a model evaluation. A full description of the evaluation is often too long to be included in the core part of a published manuscript. We advocate that the OPE documentation be presented as a technical supplement. By documenting the details of the model evaluation procedure, the OPE provides essential information for the peer-review of a modelling study and directly contributes to higher transparency. We encourage modellers to try the OPE protocol by using the word template (S1) and get help and inspiration from the answers provided in the six case studies (S2). We also encourage reviewers to use the OPE questions as a guide when evaluating modelling studies.

As noted by Grimm *et al.* (2014), building a 'culture' of model reporting is about *doing all these things as well as you can because you know that peers and model clients are expecting you to; there is no point any more in complaining about “additional effort” for these things.* We recognise that we are not there yet. Promoting the OPE and similar documentation during the peer review process would help in getting this culture in place.

The current version of the OPE protocol is a work-in-progress. Model evaluation is complex and the development of tools for reporting how evaluation is conducted is not a simple problem. During the discussions that formed the basis for the current protocol, a central point was that modellers have various cultures, experiences, and practices when it comes to model evaluation.

These points of view are not always easy to reconcile with each other. Further discussions based on the use of the protocol on a wider range of models are expected to lead to revisions of the OPE protocol in the future.

6. Conclusion

The OPE protocol is proposed as a tool to report the evaluation of ecological models. The reporting template is organised along 25 questions which make it easier and faster for modellers to report model evaluation. The OPE structure further promotes comprehensive reporting of the evaluation process, ranging from objectives, to data, skill assessment, and sensitivity analyses. Our experience is that structured reporting of model evaluation helps modellers to think more deeply about the evaluation of their models. From this last point, we suggest that it would be highly beneficial for modellers to consider the OPE early in the modelling process, in addition to using it as a reporting tool (as we have done here) and as a reviewing tool.

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8. References

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